

THE ROLE OF EXTRACURRICULAR MUSIC CLUBS IN YOUTH EDUCATION

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Annotation: This article provides detailed information on reforms in the field of culture and art, the influence of music clubs organized outside the classroom in secondary schools on the education of young people, and the development of skills for the effective organization of music clubs.

Keywords: school, club, music, education, interest, person, idea, development, territory, student, lesson.

СИНФДАН ТАШҚАРИ ТАШКИЛ ЭТИЛАДИГАН МУСИҚА ТЎГАРАКЛАРИНИНГ ЁШЛАР ТАРБИЯСИДАГИ ЎРНИ

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Аннотация: Мазкур мақолада маданият ва санъат соҳасидаги ислохотлар, умумтаълим мактабларида синфдан ташқари ташкил этиладиган мусиқа тўғаракларни ёшлар тарбиясига таъсири, мусиқа тўғаракларини фаолиятини самарали ташкил этилиши бўйича кўникмаларни ривожлантириш бўйича батафсил маълумот берилган.

Калит сўзлар: мактаб, тўғарак, мусиқа, тарбия, манфаат, инсон, ғоя, ривожланиш, ҳудуд, ўқувчи, дарс.

РОЛЬ ВНЕКЛАССНЫХ МУЗЫКАЛЬНЫХ КРУЖКОВ В ВОСПИТАНИИ МОЛОДЕЖИ

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Аннотация: В данной статье представлена подробная информация о реформах в сфере культуры и искусства, влиянии музыкальных кружков, организованных внеклассно в общеобразовательных школах, на образование молодежи, а также развитие навыков эффективной организации музыкальных кружков.

Ключевые слова: школа, кружок, музыка, образование, интерес, человек, идея, развитие, территория, ученик, урок.

The term “spiritual threat” should first of all mean ideological, ideological and informational attacks aimed at derailing the spiritual world of any person, aimed at living as a free person in the literal sense of the word. Egocentrism is a form of selfishness, which means living only by thinking about oneself and one's own interests, not recognizing anything else. In terms of the damage that this vice does to humanity, ignorance and bigotry never cease. Negative habits such as indifference, putting one's own interests above everything else, selfishness, and ambition are the main characteristics of a person suffering from egocentrism. Ideological space is the state of the not yet formed advanced ideological system that replaces it in accordance with the requirements of development, when the ideology that was previously dominant in the process of transition from the old system to the new system becomes a thing of the past. In such conditions, different ideologies try to influence this area.[1]

As a solution to these problems, it is important to raise the educational process of music clubs outside the classroom to the level of today's requirements in order to spend free time of students-young people meaningfully and usefully.

When educating students in the national spirit, musical concepts are considered an integral part of the spiritual culture of a person, which helps to control and shape a person's behavior, is considered a multifaceted quality of a person, and determines the level of upbringing, which expresses his general level of maturity. This, in turn, is related not only to the presence of various qualities, but also to the extent to which ideas embody universal qualities.

Family, school, public organizations, and mass media participate in educating students in the national spirit. The role of music clubs organized outside the classroom is of particular importance in this regard. Out-of-class networks of artistic amateur circles are increasing, which, while positively contributing to ideological education, is a sign of insufficient effectiveness. [2] The analysis of the experiences collected as a result of the research shows that the existing characters of students and the level of formation of musical education in music circles require a review of the social requirements set by society based on the requirements of the present time. Because in the education and training of students, their artistic and creative it is necessary to organize them on the basis of music circles to use their accumulated rich experience in terms of involvement in activities. This, in turn, can be seen as the reason for insufficient ideological, political and practical approach to the educational work carried out by the leaders of the circle. All of this creates important problems in the educational process of forming the concepts of the national mentality aimed at one goal. This complicates the work to be carried out in the field, causes many problems in solving problems. Because, in this field, it not only determines the moral and social description of the person, but also determines his position in the legal, political and worldview. Therefore, we should look at this problem not only as spiritual or artistic education, but also as a whole embodied political, ideological, spiritual, cultural, aesthetic, perceptive, volitional and spiritual education full of emotions.

Putting the meaning and essence of principles such as the perfect person, social cooperation, inter-ethnic harmony, and inter-religious tolerance, which are integral components of the national psyche, into the center of the spiritual-educational, educational work being carried out in our country today, raising them to a new level, raising our young generation to think independently in all aspects It consists in educating the owners of a mature worldview.

In the implementation of this task, along with the educational subject "Musical culture" in the school, the pedagogical possibilities of artistic circles in music outside the classroom are very great. Because, unlike the general high school education system, students come to art clubs with their own interests and free will, and there are many opportunities for an individual approach to classes.

The principle of individual approach reflects the tradition of teacher-disciple, which has existed in Uzbek national music art for a long time. Therefore, it is easy to form national musical values in the minds of students. The activities of musical circles should be based on the principles of education, universal values and the study of national musical masterpieces.[3]

The Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan, adopted on May 21, 2004, "On the state nationwide program for the development of school education in 2004-2009", defined a number of tasks for improving the content of education outside the school and classroom.

Changing the goals and main tasks of extracurricular music in each general secondary school, taking into account local characteristics, its directions, development prospects, community norms, rules and traditions, material and technical conditions, financial support, activity program, in the implementation of activities of extracurricular music clubs, the rights of students and teaching staff cannot be limited. [4] Taking into account the above, it is important to develop and implement measures to develop the process of extracurricular and extracurricular education in general education schools, and to increase the effectiveness of extracurricular educational institutions.

The scope of activities of extracurricular education is wide-ranging, there are certain opportunities for meaningful spending of free time of schoolchildren, and a number of activities are being carried out. [5] Along with the teaching of the subject “Musical culture” in general secondary schools, it is necessary to highlight the importance of musical and artistic clubs organized outside the classroom in the formation of the spiritual, artistic and moral culture of a number of students. Extracurricular clubs are intended to provide additional education to students as a component of the continuous education system introduced in the educational regulations of the Republic of Uzbekistan. [6] The following tasks of socio-pedagogical education of students through the medium of “Musical culture” are noted in the regulation “On non-school institution”:

- to ensure the right of students and youth to receive education outside the classroom, to provide students and youth with knowledge, skills and qualifications based on the state requirements for extracurricular education, and to achieve mastery of educational programs based on these requirements;
- the student - to meaningfully organize the free time of young people, to prevent them from falling under the influence of various foreign ideas by forming in their minds the feelings characteristic of a perfect person - patriotic feelings;
- educating young people in the spirit of respect for the traditions, culture and state language of our people and directing them to basic professions;
- regularly providing educational content that meets the interests and needs of students with advanced, national and new pedagogical technologies;
- education of attitude to work, which is the highest value of life in students;
- implementation of the concept of educational activities outside the classroom and school to provide additional education and prepare for activities in the current socio-economic conditions. In accordance with the socio-pedagogical tasks assigned to them, music outside the classroom performs the following:

They create conditions for all students from 6 to 18 years of age for their comprehensive development and meaningful organization of free time from a socio-pedagogical point of view;

- they create conditions for the development of students’ personalities, their interests, talents, independent learning and creative work;
- implement measures to strengthen the material and technical base together with local government organizations;
- study the special needs of society and some individuals and accordingly open clubs aimed at developing the creative abilities of the individual according to the interests of the children;
- provide additional education on the basics of science;
- teach children traditional national arts and crafts;

they organize and conduct competitions aimed at identifying talented and talented young people among students, personal development, tourist slots, technical and artistic creativity and other events.

References:

1. Sharipova G., Khodjayeva Z. Music teaching methodology I textbook / - Tashkent - "NIF MSH" – 2020.
2. Boymirzaev H. "Methodology of learning music". - T.: "Teacher" publishing house, 1995 .
3. Yuldoshev Sh, Usmanov S. Pedagogical technology basics. - Tashkent, - Science, 2001.
4. Tolipov K, Usmonboeva M. Practical foundations of pedagogical technologies. Tashkent "Science" 2006.
5. Panjiyev.K. Improving the Caspian training of future music teachers with the help of Uzbek folk songs. Monograph. Tashkent 2022.
6. Muslimov N.A. Professional formation of future vocational education teachers. Tashkent. Science. 2004.